

Methods for Estimating Population Density Based on Grouped and Ungrouped Line Transect Sampling

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Abstract

Abo Ehsaiyan, Hassan Mohammad Ahmad. Methods for Estimating Population Density Based on Grouped and Ungrouped Line Transect Sampling. Master of Science Thesis, Department of Statistics, Yarmouk University, 2015. (Supervisor: Prof. Omar M. Eidous).

New parametric models with two parameters are proposed to estimate the population abundance based on grouped and ungrouped line transect data. The Lomax model and the weighted Lomax models are proposed and studied. These models are flexible since they give a lot of graphs depending on the parameters selection. Also these models satisfy the monotonically decreasing property with the perpendicular distances. Moreover, the weighted Lomax models achieve the shoulder condition assumption while the shoulder condition for the un-weighted Lomax model is not satisfied. A real data set is also considered and it has been analyzed using the proposed models for two perpendicular distances data types.

Keywords: Lomax model; Weighted Lomax model; Line transect sampling; Detection function; Shoulder condition; Grouped data; Ungrouped data..

المخلص

ابو إحسان, حسن محمد أحمد . تقدير وفرة المجتمع باستخدام توزيع لوماكس ولوماكس الموزون للبيانات المجمعّة والغير مجمعّة بطريقة الخط العرضي, رسالة ماجستير في العلوم, قسم الإحصاء, جامعة اليرموك, 2015. (المشرف: الأستاذ الدكتور عمر إدوس).

في هذه الأطروحة قمنا باقتراح عدة نماذج بمعلمتين لتقدير كثافة أو وفرة المجتمع بطريقة الخط العرضي للبيانات المجمعّة والغير مجمعّة, حيث تم إقتراح ودراسة نموذج لوماكس ونماذج لوماكس الموزونة, هذه النماذج تعتبر نماذج مرنة لأنها تنتج العديد من الأشكال بالإعتماد على اختيار المعلمات داخلهما . أيضا كل من هذه النماذج يحقق خاصية التناقص الطردي مع المسافة العمودية بالإضافة إلى ان شرط الكتف متحقق فقط في نماذج لوماكس الموزونة بينما غير متحقق في نموذج لوماكس الغير موزون. حالة البيانات الحقيقية أخذت بعين الإعتبار , وتم تحليلها تحت نموذج لوماكس و نماذج لوماكس الموزونة لكلا النوعين من البيانات.

الكلمات المفتاحية: نموذج لوماكس, نموذج لوماكس الموزون, طريقة معاينة الخط العرضي, إقتران التحري أو الكشف , شرط الكتف.

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Always in all the times, all the places and all the situations. I start In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful.

No letters no words and no sentences enough to express how much I am grateful to Allah for giving me everything to reach the times and the places where I am now, I made a swear and I certify on myself that everything I do, every breathe I take, every single letter I learn and teach to others and every favor I do. I do it and seeking the way of Allah.

For the struggling men seeking for their freedom, for the people behind the bores believing in sunlight, for the martyrs, for every free man in this world. I stand with honor to say from the heart of suffer, pain and sadness these words,

**How much is tough to believe in light at the middle of the long
night,
How much is tough to believe in the snow at the middle of the hot
summer,
How beautiful is the sadness garden flower.**

I would like to express my grateful deep thanks to my parents and my family, for their faith in me, and for allowing me to be as ambitious as I wanted. It was under their watchful eye that I gained so much drive and an ability to tackle challenges head on.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION AND LITRATURE REVIEW

1.1 Introduction

As our environment and natural food resources are continually under threat, more and more scientists and wildlife managers are being made increasingly accountable for the accuracy and reliability of their results. For this reason, the Knowledge of animal abundance and the monitoring of population trends is essential today. Distance sampling methods have been developed intensively over the last thirty years and have been widely applied for sampling a number of populations especially wildlife populations. The term distance sampling includes both line and point transects methods (circular plots, trapping webs, and cue counting). Distance sampling can provide robust and peer estimation of abundance more cheaply than other distance sampling methods. The main property of distance sampling method is that not all objects within the study area have to be counted and some of these objects will be missed.

The Line transect method is a logical method for estimating the population density D (abundance) for objects distributed across large geographical area. It is the simplest, the most practical and the least expensive method among all methods of estimating the population abundance. It can provide reliable estimates of density of objects under fairly mild assumptions. In line transect method, an observer travels a randomly placed line and perpendicular distances x_i are taken from the line to

each observed object. In practical applications several lines should be used to sample the population (Figure 1.1). The sample data here are the set of perpendicular distances representing the distance from the sampled objects to the line transect. Many objects remain undetected during the survey course, this is considered as a beautiful characteristic for the line transect approach that can give an accurate estimates of population abundance even though not all objects have been detected. Sometimes undetected objects proportion is falling between (60-90%) varying from one sample size to another and regarding to the study conditions (Buckland *et al.*, 2001).

The probability of detecting an object near to the line transect center is greater than the probability of detecting an object away from the line center. This probability is modeled under a function named the detection function $g(x)$, which is defined by

$$g(x) = P(\text{an object is detected} \mid \text{its perpendicular distance is } x).$$

The hypothesised detection function $g(x)$ is considered to be as the essential concept of the line transect method. The logical assumption about $g(x)$ is that $g(x)$ is monotonically decreasing in x , which means that the detection process decreases as the perpendicular distance from the line center increases. This can be expressed mathematically as $g(x_i) \geq g(x_i + 1)$ where $x_i < x_i + 1$. Another logical assumption about $g(x)$ is that $g(0) = 1$, which means that the probability of detecting an object on the line transect center should remain certain. That is, the object directly on the transect line will never be missed. Another assumption is that the detection function for different sub-regions is identical.

Figure (1.1). A single line transect of length L was randomly-placed, Six objects were detected with perpendicular distances x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6 .

Let $f(x)$ be the probability density function (*pdf*) from which the perpendicular distances x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are drawn. Burnham and Anderson (1976) showed that $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are related such that

$$f(x) = g(x) / \int_0^{\infty} g(x) dx, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \infty. \quad (1.1)$$

Therefore, the perpendicular distance x of any observed object will tend to have a probability density function (*pdf*) $f(x)$ of the same shape as $g(x)$ but scaled therefore the area under $f(x)$ equals unity.

Given that L is the total length of k lines l_1, l_2, \dots, l_k , which are assumed to be non-overlapping, straight and placed randomly in a specific region (Figure 1.2) and let n be the number of sighted (observed) objects collected based on the k lines. Burnham and Anderson (1976) derived the relationship between $f(0)$ which is $f(x)$ at $x = 0$ and the population abundance D , which is given by

$$D = \frac{E(n)f(0)}{2L} \quad (1.2)$$

where $E(n)$ is the expected value of the number of detected objects. As Formula (1.2) demonstrated that the estimation of D needs the estimation of the parameter $f(0)$. Therefore, the estimation of D is equivalent to the estimation of $f(0)$.

Figure (1.2). Diagram represents straight, non- overlapping and random six parallel lines ($k = 6$) of lengths l_1, l_2, \dots, l_6 and $L = \sum_{i=1}^k l_i$.

Let $\hat{f}(0)$ be an appropriate sample estimator for $f(0)$ based on n observed perpendicular distances x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . Burnham and Anderson (1976) introduced the general estimator for D , which is given by

$$\hat{D} = \frac{n\hat{f}(0)}{2L}. \quad (1.3)$$

Formula (1.3) states that if $\hat{f}(0)$ is the sample estimator of $f(0)$, then $\hat{f}(0)$ plays the crucial role in estimating D . Actually, the main idea in line transect sampling is the estimation of $f(0)$ as well as modeling of $f(x)$.

There are two methods to accomplish the estimation procedure. The two methods are the parametric and the non-parametric. The parametric method fundamentally assumes that the *pdf* $f(x, \theta)$ is known with unknown parameter θ also it requires that $f(x, \theta)$ belongs to a family of proper probability density function. However, the functional form of $f(x, \theta)$ depends on unknown parameter θ , where θ may take a vector value and should be estimated based on the perpendicular distances x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . The maximum likelihood (ML) method and the method of moments (MM) are the most popular statistical techniques of point estimation that can be used to estimate θ and then to estimate $f(0, \theta)$.

Despite recent developments in nonparametric methods, parametric method remains important and widely used because of its simplicity. The parametric method performs well if the model fitted the data at hand correctly. However, its performance is not acceptable when the perpendicular distances deviated from the selected *pdf* (Burnham *et al.*, 1980). In such a case, the alternative method to estimate $f(0)$ and D is

the nonparametric method. The nonparametric method mainly assumes nothing about the form or the shape of the detection function. As a nonparametric method examples the Fourier series (Burnham *et al.*, 1980), and the kernel method (Chen, 1996) are the most well known nonparametric methods in the field of line transect sampling.

Eidous and collaborators have made significant contributions to line transect sampling by developing flexible statistical models for population density estimation. Early work introduced combination and semi-parametric models (Eidous, 2003, 2006), which were later extended to address violations of the shoulder condition (Eidous, 2012a, 2012b, 2015). Various kernel-based approaches—such as half-normal, double kernel, and fourth-order methods (Eidous, 2009; Eidous and Shakhathreh, 2012; Eidous and Al-Masri, 2010)—enhanced estimation accuracy. Further developments included histogram models (Eidous, 2014), kernel-exponential models (Eidous and Al-Masri, 2006), and the use of AIC for model selection (Eidous and Al-Salman, 2013). Together, these studies provide a strong set of methods for estimating population density in ecological research.

1.2 The Shoulder Condition

Burnham *et al.* (1980) suggested a logical assumption about the detection function $g(x)$, which is $g(x)$ should have a “shoulder” at the origin. The validity of the shoulder condition in the line transect method means : the probability of detecting an object in a narrow area around the line transect remains certain or remains very close to one (Figure 1.3). That is, the probability of detecting an object that has a small perpendicular

distance is very high. Mathematically, when the shoulder condition is assumed to be satisfied (true) then the first derivative of the detection function at $x = 0$ equals zero (i.e. $g'(0) = 0$). Otherwise, the shoulder condition is said to be not satisfied (not true). The condition $g'(0) = 0$ implies that $f'(0) = 0$. This can be illustrated as follows: Since $f(x)$ is given by

$$f(x) = g(x) / \int_0^{\infty} g(x) dx \text{ then } f'(0) = \left[\int_0^{\infty} g(x) dx \right]^{-1} g'(0).$$

It can be noticed that if $g'(0) = 0$ then $f'(0) = 0$ (Buckland *et al.*, 2001). A truncation point (w) might be reasonable to eliminate some outliers where the perpendicular distances after this point won't be considered. In this case the range of x is $(0 \leq x \leq w)$ (Figure 1.3).

Figure (1.3). Detection in a very narrow distance from line transect center should remain certain. That is, the shoulder condition is satisfied, the range of x is $(0 \leq x \leq w)$.

1.3 Ungrouped and Grouped Perpendicular Distances

Our objects of interest (distance data) can be recorded exactly (accurately) or grouped. When we make a rounding for the errors in measurements this usually cause the data to be grouped to some degree, but they must be analyzed as if they had been recorded accurately, or grouped further, in order to alleviate the effects of rounding on the bias of resultant estimators. Distances are often assigned to predetermined distance intervals, and must then be analyzed using methods developed for the analysis of frequency data.

1.3.1 Ungrouped Perpendicular Distances

By the ungrouped data we mean that the objects of interest are recorded accurately (exactly) without the need of rounding errors in measurements. In this case we directly use the proposed model to estimate the parameters of interest related to this model using any robust estimation method such as the method of moments or the maximum likelihood method. The estimation of $\hat{f}(0)$ and consequently D (Formula, 1.3) are then obtained based on a random based of specific size.

1.3.2 Grouped Perpendicular Distances

The root cause of correctly allocating objects into distance intervals is to achieve robustness in the analysis of data that showing systematic errors such as heaping (i.e. rounding errors) and inaccurate field measurements (i.e. objects movement prior detection). The general statistical theory and

the field experience indicate that little efficiency is lost by grouping the data (Buckland *et al.*, 2001).

Burnham *et al.* (1980) proposed two reasons for arising analysis of grouped data. The first reason is that the line transect data are sometimes recorded as ungrouped and after collecting data we analyze it as grouped, grouping into distance intervals is sometimes necessary to achieve robustness in the analysis of data that showing systematic errors such as heaping (i.e. rounding errors). The second reason for grouping is sometimes it is necessary to achieve robustness, due to problems of data recoding or inaccurate field measurements (i.e. objects movement prior detection).

Assume that the data of perpendicular distances were taken in the field only by intervals, or that, for some situations, the perpendicular distances must be analyzed as grouped data. Let n be the number of perpendicular distances are classified to whether they fall into k cells. If each distance independently falls into one of the intervals with probability P_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, then the distribution of n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k is multinomial with index n and probabilities P_1, P_2, \dots, P_k where n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k is number of perpendicular distances falling into k intervals, where $n = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i$, n is total sample size and n_i is the number of perpendicular distances falling in the i^{th} intervals. For similar scheme it is natural, at least in large samples, to use unbiased estimator of P_i , the relative frequency,

$$P_i = \frac{n_i}{n}, i = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

In smaller samples, the relative frequency is not so compelling. The theory of grouped line transects data analysis using maximum likelihood estimation was presented by Burnham *et al.*(1980) who stated that, if

$f(x)$ is any probability density function model for the ungrouped perpendicular distance data, then an estimator of $f(0)$ can validly be based on the model using grouped data, as in the case of ungrouped perpendicular data. Let the perpendicular distances be grouped into k intervals by cut points (boundaries) $c_0 < c_1 < \dots < c_k$; the i^{th} interval is (c_{i-1}, c_i) with $c_0 = 0$ and $c_k = w$, w may be chosen to be larger than the largest perpendicular distance. There still exist an underlying, continuous detection function and corresponding density function. Because each detected object will fall into one of the k mutually exclusive intervals, the probabilities P_1, P_2, \dots, P_k sum to one ($\sum_{i=1}^k P_i = 1$).

Under the multinomial probability distribution of n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k , the probability of the observed frequency counts is given by

$$Pr(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = \frac{n!}{n_1!n_2!\dots n_k!} P_1^{n_1} P_2^{n_2} \dots P_k^{n_k}. \quad (1.4)$$

In order to link the model $f(x)$ to the grouped data properly requires that P_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are formally expressible as functions of the parameters under the proposed model. Therefore, each cell probability P_i has a form expression

$$P_i = \int_{c_{i-1}}^{c_i} f(x) dx = F(c_i) - F(c_{i-1}) \quad (1.5)$$

where $F(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function corresponding the density function $f(x)$, and P_i is a function of the parameters that arise in $f(x)$.

1.4 Literature Review

This section is divided into two subsections. The first one gives some prominent parametric models that have been used in line transect sampling. The other one introduces the nonparametric methods that have been used in the scope of line transect sampling technique.

1.4.1 Literature Review of Parametric Models

Let $f(x; \theta)$ be an unknown *pdf* of perpendicular distances, a parametric approach presumes that $f(x; \theta)$ is the *pdf* of known functional form but depend on unknown parameter θ , where θ may take a vector value and should be estimated by using the perpendicular distances. Variety approaches to estimate θ will be legitimately leading to $\hat{f}(0) = f(0, \hat{\theta})$. A number of feasible parametric models have been proposed for $f(x; \theta)$ and there is an extensive trend on the use of maximum likelihood techniques for estimation of $f(0; \theta)$. With one scale parameter, the classical exponential and the half normal models are the most prominent models. Gates *et al.* (1968) suggested the negative exponential detection function $g(x; \alpha) = e^{-x/\alpha}$, $x \geq 0$, $\alpha \geq 0$, with *pdf* is given by

$$f(x; \alpha) = \frac{e^{-x/\alpha}}{\alpha}, \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha \geq 0 \quad . \quad (1.6)$$

Because $g'(0; \alpha) \neq 0$, and consequently $f'(0; \alpha) \neq 0$, which obviously indicates that $g(x)$ do not satisfy the shoulder condition, so detection function was very restrictive and might be inappropriate in many application cases (Buckland *et al.*, 2001). Therefore, there is a limitation of

utilizing this model in line transect sampling. Now, let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of size n perpendicular distances follow the negative exponential $f(x; \alpha)$ and the ML estimator of $f(0; \alpha)$ is $\hat{f}_{MLE}(0; \alpha) = \frac{1}{\hat{\alpha}}$, where $\hat{\alpha} = \bar{X}$ is the sample mean. Therefore, the ultimate estimator of the population abundance (Formula, 1.3) becomes $\hat{D} = \frac{nf(0; \hat{\alpha})}{2L} = \frac{n}{2L\bar{X}}$.

Hemingway (1971) suggested the half-normal model to estimate the parameter $f(0; \sigma^2)$ with detection function $g(x; \sigma^2) = e^{-x^2/\sigma^2}$, $x \geq 0$, and the corresponding *pdf* is given by

$$f(x; \sigma^2) = \frac{2}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2}, x \geq 0. \quad (1.7)$$

The half-normal model detection function satisfy the shoulder condition Since $g'(0; \sigma^2) = \frac{-x}{\sigma^2} e^{-x^2/\sigma^2}$, which gives $g'(0; \sigma^2) = 0$. Based on X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n random sample of size n perpendicular distances follow the half-normal $f(x; \sigma^2)$ and the ML estimator of $f(0; \sigma^2)$ is $\hat{f}_{3,MLE}(0; \hat{\sigma}^2) = \left(\frac{2}{\pi\hat{\sigma}}\right)^{1/2}$, where $\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2/n}$. So the ultimate estimator of the population abundance (Formula, 1.3) becomes $\hat{D} = \frac{nf(0; \hat{\sigma})}{2L} = \frac{n}{\hat{\sigma} L\sqrt{2\pi}}$, where $\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2/n}$.

Pollock (1978) proposed the exponential power series with two-parameter λ and p with detection function $g(x; p, \lambda) = e^{-(x/\lambda)^p}$, and the corresponding *pdf* is given by

$$f(x; p, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda\Gamma(1+1/p)} e^{-(x/\lambda)^p}, x > 0, \lambda, p > 0. \quad (1.8)$$

So $f(0; p, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda\Gamma(1+1/p)}$. This model incorporates the negative exponential and the half normal as special cases. For $p = 1$ the resulting

model is the negative exponential model and $p = 2$ the half-normal model is resulted.

Burnham *et al.* (1980) suggested another two-parameter model that includes negative exponential and half normal as special cases. The model is the exponential quadratic model with probability density function

$$f(x; \alpha, \theta) = \frac{1}{\mu} e^{-\alpha x - \theta x^2}, x > 0, \alpha, \theta > 0 \quad (1.9)$$

where μ is a normalizing constant, $\mu = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\alpha x - \theta x^2} dx$. The corresponding detection function is $g(x; \alpha, \theta) = e^{-\alpha x - \theta x^2}$. Recall that the parameter we are interested to estimate is $f(0; \alpha, \theta) = \frac{1}{\mu}$, where μ is a normalizing constant which is a function of α and θ . Quinn and Gallucci (1980) derived the minimum variance unbiased estimator for $f(0)$ under the half normal Model (1.7), which is given by

$$\hat{f}_{3,MV}(0) = \frac{1}{\beta(n)} \left(\frac{2}{\pi T} \right)^{1/2}, \text{ where } \beta(n) = \frac{\Gamma((n-1)/2)}{\Gamma(n/2)} \left(\frac{n}{2} \right)^{1/2}.$$

Eberhardt (1968) recommended the reverse logistic model with two parameters α and γ with detection function $g(x) = \frac{(1+\gamma)e^{-\alpha x}}{1+\gamma e^{-\alpha x}}$, and the corresponding *pdf* is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{\alpha \gamma e^{-\alpha x}}{\ln(1+\gamma)(1+\gamma e^{-\alpha x})}, x > 0, \alpha, \gamma > 0. \quad (1.10)$$

Therefore, $g(0) = \frac{\alpha \gamma}{\ln(1+\gamma)(1+\gamma)}$. Eberhardt (1968) used the reverse logistic model as a reference for simulation of line transect sampling. Hays and Buckland (1983) proposed the hazard rate model to fit the line transect data. This model was further studied by Buckland (1985), who suggested the Hermite polynomial model for grouped line transect data. Karunmamuni and Quinn (1995) developed a Bayesian model for estimating the density of animal population from data obtained by line

transect method. A Bayesian estimator is constructed with respect to gamma prior density. Eidous (2004) suggested the half- t –model to fit the line transect data with detection function $g(x) = \left(1 + \frac{x^2}{\theta_1\theta_2}\right)^{-(\theta_1+1/2)}$, and the corresponding pdf is given by

$$f(x, \theta_1, \theta_2) = \frac{2(\theta_1+1/2)}{\sqrt{\pi\theta_1\theta_2}(\theta_1/2)} g(x), \quad x \geq 0. \quad (1.11)$$

Zhang (2009) proposed the shrinkage estimator under half-normal Model (1.7), which is given by $\hat{f}_{3,SH}(0) = \frac{n-2}{n} \beta(n) \left(\frac{2}{\pi T}\right)^{1/2}$. The estimator $\hat{f}_{3,SH}(0)$ is biased for $f(0)$, but has the smallest mean square error. The shrinkage estimator is a kind of estimators where we sacrifice the unbiasedness property to minimize the variance or the mean square error. There is a relationship between the three estimators $\hat{f}_{3,MLE}(0)$, $\hat{f}_{3,MV}(0)$ and $\hat{f}_{3,SH}(0)$ which can be derived easily as follows:

$$\hat{f}_{3,SH}(0) = \frac{n-2}{n} B^2(n) \hat{f}_{3,MV}(0) = \frac{n-2}{n} B(n) \hat{f}_{3,MLE}(0).$$

The function $\beta(n) \rightarrow 1$ (Magnus *et al.*, 1966) and $\frac{n-2}{n} \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, and from the asymptotic viewpoint, the three estimators are equivalent $\hat{f}_{3,SH}(0) = \hat{f}_{3,MV}(0) = \hat{f}_{3,MLE}(0)$. Al-Ababneh and Eidous (2012) suggested another model with detection function,

$$g(x; \theta, \gamma) = 2e^{-\theta x} - e^{-\gamma x}, \quad x \geq 0, \theta, \gamma > 0. \quad (1.12)$$

According to this detection function, the probability of detecting an object given that its perpendicular distance $x = 0$ is one (i.e. $g(0; \theta, \gamma) = 1$). On the other hand, the first derivative of $g(x; \theta, \gamma)$ at $x = 0$ is $-2\theta + \gamma$ (i.e. $g'(0; \theta, \gamma) = -2\theta + \gamma$), which indicates that $g(x; \theta, \gamma)$ do not satisfy

the shoulder condition unless $\gamma = 2\theta$. Therefore and by taking $\gamma = 2\theta$, Al-Ababneh and Eidous (2012) suggested the following detection function

$$g(x; \theta) = e^{-\theta x}(2 - e^{-\theta x}), x \geq 0, \theta > 0. \quad (1.13)$$

Model (1.13) is now satisfies the shoulder condition. The corresponding *pdf* is given by,

$$f(x; \theta) = \frac{2\theta}{3} e^{-\theta x}(2 - e^{-\theta x}), x \geq 0, \theta > 0. \quad (1.14)$$

Since $g(0; \theta) = 1$ then $f(0; \theta) = \frac{2\theta}{3}$. The above model can be expressed in terms of $f(0)$ as follows

$$f(x) = f(0; \theta)e^{-3f(0; \theta) x / 2}(2 - e^{-3f(0; \theta) x / 2}), x \geq 0. \quad (1.15)$$

Under model (1.15), Al-Ababneh and Eidous (2012) derived the expected value of x which is given by $7/(9f(0))$. This leads to $\hat{f}_{MO}(0) = 7/(9\bar{x})$ as the moments estimator for $f(0)$. Al-Saeed (2013) proposed the weighted exponential model for grouped and ungrouped line transect data with detection function $g(x; \theta, \beta) = e^{-\theta x}(2 - e^{-\theta x})^\beta, x \geq 0, \theta, \beta > 0$, and the corresponding *pdf* is given by,

$$f(x; \theta, \beta) = \frac{2\theta\Gamma(\beta+1/2)}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(\beta+1)+\Gamma(\beta+1/2)} e^{-\theta x}(2 - e^{-\theta x})^\beta, x \geq 0, \theta, \beta > 0. \quad (1.16)$$

Since the guiding yardstick for the above models assumes that the form of the probability density function is known then they are known as parametric methods. The parametric methods are better than non parametric methods if the proposed model is chosen to be appropriate for the line transect data at hand (Buckland *et al.*, 2001).

1.4.2 Literature Review of Nonparametric Methods

To avoid the assumption about the shape of the detectable functions the nonparametric density estimation methods might be useful instead of the parametric methods. The Fourier series model for analysis perpendicular distance data from line transect sampling was proposed by Burnham *et al.* (1980). They published a major monograph on line transect sampling theory and application. Their work provided a review of previous methods, they gave guidelines for field use, and identified a small class of estimators that seemed to be useful. Theoretical and numerical studies led them to recommend the use of estimators based on the Fourier series. In the last years; researchers have turned their attention to nonparametric kernel method, which becomes an important tool in wildlife sampling. Some modern efforts using kernel methods were made by Buckland (1992) and Chen (1996). Mack (1998) used the kernel method to perform a test concerning the validity of the shoulder condition assumption. Barabesi (2000) proposed a semi-parametric technique based on local parametric density estimation. Mack (2002) considered some methods of bias correction when the kernel method is used in constructing confidence intervals for wildlife abundance based on transect data. Gerad and Schucanty (2002) investigated a method for combining estimators from individual transects when each transect has sufficient data to support estimation with the kernel method. It is based on a minimization of the asymptotic mean square error of linear combination of the individual population density estimator. Eidous (2005a) proposed some methods to improve the performance of the kernel estimator using line transect data. Eidous (2005b) introduced the histogram estimator and investigated its

performances using line transect data. Another adaptation of the histogram estimator is suggested and investigated by Eidous (2011). He developed this estimator under the assumption that the shoulder condition assumption is not valid. Al-Bdareen (2011) studied two new estimators for estimating $f(0)$, which can be considered as a modification for the kernel estimator. Al-Momani (2011) suggested and studied two new estimators for the population density in both cases when the data have a shoulder at the origin and when they don't have. Abu-Sbeih (2013) makes a generalization to the work of Al-Momani (2011). Al-Ababneh (2012) and Al-Shboul (2012) developed new estimators for $f(0)$ when the data of line transects are combined together before the analysis and when the data are dealt separately for each line. While Al-Ababneh used the kernel method to perform her goals, Al-Shboul used the histogram method to achieve the same goals. Finally, Eidous and Al-shakhatreh (2011) investigated the properties of a semi-parametric estimator for $f(0)$ that combines between the kernel estimator and a specific parametric estimator. The parametric estimator is chosen to be the half normal or negative exponential based on testing the shoulder condition assumption.

1.5 Statement of Problem and Objectives

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be n perpendicular distances (assumed to be independent and identically distributed) following the detection function $g(x; \alpha, \beta)$, where α and β are two unknown parameters and $f(x; \alpha, \beta) = k g(x; \alpha, \beta)$, where $k = 1/\int_0^\infty g(x; \alpha, \beta) dx$.

The Lomax detection function is proposed to be

$$g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0.$$

Since $g'_1(0, \alpha, \beta) = -\beta(1 + \alpha) \neq 0$ then the Lomax detection function $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ do not satisfy the shoulder condition assumption. As another proposed models, we consider the following two detection functions and refer to them as “weighted Lomax detection functions”, which are proposed to be,

$$g_2(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{2}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \right) \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0$$

and

$$g_3(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{4}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\frac{\alpha+1}{2}}} \right)^2 \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0$$

Because $g'_2(0, \alpha, \beta) = g'_3(0, \alpha, \beta) = 0$, then $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ have shoulder condition at the origin. We notice that $g_1(0, \alpha, \beta) = g_2(0, \alpha, \beta) = g_3(0, \alpha, \beta) = 1$ and the corresponding *pdfs* of $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ respectively are

$$f_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0, \quad (1.17)$$

$$f_2(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \frac{2}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \right) \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0 \quad (1.18)$$

and

$$f_3(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \frac{4}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x)^{\frac{\alpha+1}{2}}} \right)^2 \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0 \quad (1.19)$$

In this thesis, parametric estimators for $f(0)$ will be developed under the above Lomax and the weighted Lomax models, where two models satisfy the shoulder condition assumption but the other one does not. We aim to

develop new estimators under these three models for the two cases of data; ungrouped and grouped lines transect data.

1.7 Thesis Organization

The thesis is organized according to our goals as follows: Chapter 2 introduces new estimators under the proposed Lomax model $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$. The model depends on two parameters and the estimators are derived for both data cases; grouped and ungrouped lines transect data. In Chapter 3 we developed new estimators under the proposed weighted Lomax models $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$, the two data cases grouped and ungrouped lines transect data were also considered in this chapter. In Chapter 4 a numerical example with real data set is investigated and studied. In Chapter 5, the final conclusions and suggestions for future works are introduced.

CHAPTER TWO

LOMAX MODEL FOR UNGROUPED AND GROUPED LINE TRANSECT DATA

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter we propose a new parametric model called Lomax model to estimate the parameter $f(0)$ and D . Two types of data; ungrouped and grouped are considered under this model. The maximum likelihood and the moments estimators are derived.

2.2 The Proposed Model

The Lomax distribution is known as Pareto distribution of the second kind or Pearson Type VI distribution. There is a relationship between the Lomax distribution and some other distributions. These distributions are Weibull distribution, Compound Weibull distribution which is called the three parameter Burr type XII distribution, exponential distribution, Rayleigh distribution, beta type II, beta type I distribution, uniform distribution, generalized uniform distribution, and extreme value distribution.

Lomax or Pareto II, distribution was firstly pioneered to model business failure data (Lomax, 1954). This distribution has been widely applied in a variety of fields such as size of cities, actuarial science, medical and biological sciences and engineering. This model has been used for reliability modeling and life testing (Hassan and Al-Ghamdi, 2009) and applied to income and wealth distribution data (Harris, 1968; Atkinson and

Harrison, 1978), firm size (Corbelini *et al.*, 2007) and queuing problems. Also, it has been applied for modeling the distribution of the sizes of computer files on servers (Holland *et al.*, 2006). Bryson (1974) have suggested the use of the Lomax distribution as an alternative to the exponential distribution when the data are heavy-tailed. We suggest applying the un-weighted and weighted Lomax distributions for the line transect data in order to estimate the population abundance of objects under both data types; ungrouped and grouped.

Now let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be n perpendicular distances (assumed to be independent and identically distributed) following the detection function $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$. The proposed Lomax detection function with two parameters is given by

$$g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \alpha, \beta > 0.$$

The *pdf* that corresponds $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = k g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, where $k = 1/\int_0^{\infty} g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) dx$. Because

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) dx &= \int_0^{\infty} (1 + \beta x)^{-\alpha-1} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha\beta} \end{aligned}$$

then the *pdf* of X is

$$f_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \quad , \quad x \geq 0, \alpha, \beta > 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Note that, if X is a random variable with *pdf* $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ then we represent it by $X \sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$.

Now since $g'_1(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{-\beta(\alpha+1)}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}}$ and $g'_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = -\beta(1 + \alpha) \neq 0$, then the Lomax distribution does not satisfy the shoulder condition assumption. Some shapes of the Lomax detection function model for some values of α and β are displayed in Figure (2.1).

2.3 Moments Estimator under Ungrouped Data.

By referring to Subsection (1.3.1) and under the ungrouped data, the objects of interest can be recorded exactly (accurately). It is known that if the sample was representative for the population then the characteristics of this sample must be close to the characteristics of the population from which this sample is drawn. We can use the method of moments to estimate the parameters α and β and then $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta$. Fortunately, the estimators exist in a closed form. To use the moments method, we need to find the first and the second moments for the Lomax distribution. In general, the k^{th} moment for the Lomax distribution (i.e. when $\sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$) is,

$$E X^k = \int_0^{\infty} x^k \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} dx$$

By using the transformation $u = \frac{1}{1+\beta x}$ then $x = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{u} - 1 \right)$ and $dx = \frac{-1}{\beta u^2} du$. Therefore,

Figure (2.1). Some shapes of the Lomax detection function model for some values of α and β . $\alpha = 0.5, 2, 5, 8$ and $\beta = 0.8$.

$$\begin{aligned}
E X^k &= \alpha \int_0^1 \frac{1}{\beta^k} \left(\frac{1}{u} - 1\right)^k u^{\alpha+1} \frac{1}{u^2} du \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{u} - 1\right)^k u^{\alpha-1} du \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \int_0^1 \frac{1}{u^k} (1-u)^k u^{\alpha-1} du \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-k-1} (1-u)^{k+1-1} du \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha-k)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, \alpha > k.
\end{aligned}$$

Notice that, if $f(u) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha-k)\Gamma(k+1)} u^{\alpha-k-1} (1-u)^{k+1-1}$, $0 < u < 1$ then $f(u)$ is a beta distribution with parameters $\alpha - k$ and $k + 1$. In this case, the integral of $f(u)$ over the interval $(0, 1)$ is 1. This result is used in finding the last integral in $E X^k$. It is worthwhile to mention here that if X has a Lomax distribution with parameters α and β (i.e. $X \sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$) then according to the above integrals we obtain

$$E X^k = \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha-k)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, \alpha > k. \quad (2.2)$$

By taking $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ in (2.2) then we obtain the first and the second moments of the Lomax distribution respectively, which are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
EX &= \frac{1}{\beta(\alpha-1)}, \quad \alpha > 1, \beta > 0 \\
E X^2 &= \frac{2}{\beta^2(\alpha-1)(\alpha-2)}, \quad \alpha > 2, \beta > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

2.3.1 Moments Estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ when α is Known

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of n perpendicular distances from Lomax distribution and let \bar{X} be the sample mean. If α is assumed to be known then to find the moments estimator of β we have to solve the following equation

$$EX = \bar{X}$$

That is, we need to solve the following equation with respect to β ,

$$\frac{1}{\beta(\alpha - 1)} = \bar{X},$$

which gives,

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{1}{\bar{X}(\alpha - 1)}.$$

Therefore, the moment estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta$ is

$$\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \beta) = \frac{\alpha}{\bar{X}(\alpha - 1)}, \quad \alpha > 1.$$

As indicated in Section (1.4), if the random sample of perpendicular distances follow the negative exponential model then the moments and the maximum likelihood estimator of $f(0)$ is

$$\hat{f}(0) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}}.$$

By comparing the two estimators $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \beta)$ and $\hat{f}(0)$ and since $\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1} > 1$ for $\alpha > 1$ then we conclude that

$$\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \beta) > \hat{f}(0),$$

which indicates that $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \beta)$ is an overestimate of $\hat{f}(0)$ for any value of $\alpha > 1$. The two estimators are equivalent when $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, because in this case $\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1} \rightarrow 1$.

2.3.2 Moments Estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ when β is Known

By using the same notations in the previous subsection and by assuming that β is known then the moments estimator of α is obtained by solving the equation,

$$\frac{1}{\beta(\alpha - 1)} = \bar{X},$$

With respect to α , which gives

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\beta\bar{X}} + 1, \quad \beta > 0.$$

Therefore, the moments estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta$ when β is known is

$$\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} + \beta, \quad \beta > 0.$$

Again, by comparing $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha)$ with $\hat{f}(0) = 1/\bar{X}$, we conclude that

$$\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha) > \hat{f}(0),$$

which indicates that $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha)$ is an overestimate of $\hat{f}(0)$ for any value of $\beta > 0$. The two estimators $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha)$ and $\hat{f}(0)$ are equals when $\beta \rightarrow 0$.

2.3.3 Moments Estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ when α and β are Unknown

The moments estimators of the parameters α and β can be founded by solving the following two equations simultaneously,

$$EX = \bar{X} \quad \text{and} \quad EX^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n}$$

That is, we need to solve,

$$\frac{1}{\beta(\alpha - 1)} = \bar{X}$$

and

$$\frac{2}{\beta^2(\alpha - 1)(\alpha - 2)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n},$$

With respect to α and β . From the last two equations, we obtain

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\hat{\beta}\bar{X}} + 1, \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$\frac{2}{\hat{\beta}^2\hat{\alpha}^2 - 3\hat{\beta}^2\hat{\alpha} + 2\hat{\beta}^2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n}. \quad (2.4)$$

By substituting the value of $\hat{\alpha}$ from (2.3) back into (2.4), we obtain,

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} - \frac{2n\bar{X}}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}.$$

The value of $\hat{\beta}$ is now substitute in (2.3) to obtain $\hat{\alpha}$, which is given by

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - 2n\bar{X}^2} + 1.$$

Therefore, the moments estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta$ is,

$$\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{2}{\bar{X}} - \frac{2n\bar{X}}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}.$$

Note that the moments estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ is $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \alpha, \beta) = \hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}$ and since $\hat{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\hat{\beta}\bar{X}} + 1$ then $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \alpha, \beta)$ can re-written as $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} + \hat{\beta}$, which indicates that $\hat{f}_{M_1}(0; \alpha, \beta) > \hat{f}(0) = 1/\bar{X}$.

The results of this subsection and that of Subsections (2.3.1) and (2.3.2) show that the moments estimators of $f(0)$ under Lomax model with two parameters α and β are greater than the estimator $\hat{f}(0) = 1/\bar{X}$ that derived under the negative exponential model with one scale parameter. It is well known in the literature that the estimator $\hat{f}(0) = 1/\bar{X}$ is an over estimate of $f(0)$ in most reasonable cases of line transect data. This leads

to the fact that the moments estimators derived under the Lomax model are not acceptable estimators because all of them are greater than the estimator $\hat{f}(0) = 1/\bar{X}$. However, the maximum likelihood estimators of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ for ungrouped and for grouped data are derived in the next two sections to investigate whether or not that the maximum likelihood method gives good estimators.

2.4 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$

Maximum Likelihood Estimator is used to obtain parameter estimates and a measure of their precision under full distributional assumptions. To find maximum likelihood estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ we first need to find the maximum likelihood estimator for parameters α and β . The likelihood function based on model (2.1) is

$$l(\alpha, \beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{(\alpha\beta)^n}{\prod_{i=1}^n (1 + \beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}}$$

The log likelihood function is

$$\log l(\alpha, \beta) = n \log(\alpha) + n \log(\beta) - (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + \beta x_i).$$

We can obtain the maximum likelihood estimators for α and β by solving the following two equations simultaneously,

$$\frac{\partial \log l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \log l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{n}{\alpha} - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + \beta x_i)$$

which gives,

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + \hat{\beta} x_i)} \quad (2.5)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = \frac{n}{\beta} - (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{(1 + \beta x_i)} \quad (2.6)$$

By substituting the value of $\hat{\alpha}$ from (2.5) into (2.6) then the problem is reduced to solve the following one equation numerically,

$$\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i / (1/\hat{\beta} + x_i)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + \hat{\beta} x_i)}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i / (1 + \hat{\beta} x_i)}.$$

The value of $\hat{\beta}$ obtained from the last equation can be substituted back into (2.5) to obtain the maximum likelihood estimator $\hat{\alpha}$ of α .

The solution of the last equation can be found by using a suitable numerical algorithm method such as the Newton-Raphson method. If $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ are the maximum likelihood estimators for α and β respectively, then the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ is $f_{ML1}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) = \hat{\alpha} \hat{\beta}$ and consequently the maximum likelihood estimator of D is

$$\hat{D} = \frac{n f_{ML1}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})}{2L}.$$

As $n \rightarrow \infty$, $f_{ML1}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ is asymptotically $N(f_1(0; \alpha, \beta), \sigma_f^2)$, where

$$\sigma_f^2 = \frac{1}{n} A' I^{-1}(\alpha, \beta) A.$$

The column vector

$$A' = \left[\frac{\partial \log f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \quad \frac{\partial \log f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} \right]$$

and

$$I(\alpha, \beta) = \begin{pmatrix} -E \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha^2} \right] & -E \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right] \\ -E \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right] & -E \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta^2} \right] \end{pmatrix},$$

which is known as the Fisher information matrix. The estimator of vector A can be accomplished by using $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ as an estimators of α and β respectively. Also, the Fisher information matrix $I(\alpha, \beta)$ can be estimated by using the empirical Hessian matrix $H(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ with elements (Buckland *et al.* 2001)

$$H(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha^2} \right] & -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right] \\ -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right] & -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta^2} \right] \end{pmatrix}_{\substack{\alpha=\hat{\alpha} \\ \beta=\hat{\beta}}}.$$

Therefore, the estimator of σ_f^2 is

$$\hat{\sigma}_f^2 = \frac{1}{n} \hat{A}' H^{-1}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) \hat{A}.$$

From the above discussion, one can derive the approximate confidence interval of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ if that is required.

2.5 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta)$ (Grouped Data)

By referring to Subsection (1.3.2) and by using the same notations mentioned there which indicate that each cell probability P_i has the following expression $P_i = \int_{c_{i-1}}^{c_i} f_1(x_i; \alpha, \beta) dx = F_1(c_i) - F_1(c_{i-1}), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. The function $F_1(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function

corresponding the Lomax density function $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (Formula, 2.1). To obtain $F_1(x)$,

$$F_1(x) = p(X \leq x) = \alpha\beta \int_0^x (1 + \beta t)^{-(\alpha+1)} dt$$

By using the transformation $u = 1 + \beta t$ we obtain $t = \frac{u-1}{\beta}$ and $dt = 1/\beta du$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(x) &= \alpha \int_1^{1+\beta x} u^{-\alpha-1} du \\ &= 1 - (1 + \beta x)^{-\alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} P_i &= F_1(c_i) - F_1(c_{i-1}) \\ &= (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \end{aligned}$$

Now, for given grouped data set, the log likelihood function is defined by (Burnham *et al.*, 1980)

$$\begin{aligned} \log l_G(\alpha, \beta) &= \log \left(\frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! \dots n_k!} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \log P_i . \\ &= \log \left(\frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! \dots n_k!} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \log [(1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha}] . \end{aligned}$$

The maximum likelihood estimator of α and β are the solutions of the following two equations

$$\frac{\partial \log l_G(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l_G(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \log l_G(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} &= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \alpha} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} ((1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \log(1 + \beta c_i) - (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} \log(1 + \beta c_{i-1})) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \frac{((1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \log(1 + \beta c_i) - (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} \log(1 + \beta c_{i-1}))}{(1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha}}.
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \log l_G(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} &= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \beta} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} (\alpha(1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha-1} c_i - \alpha(1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha-1} c_{i-1}) \\
&= \alpha \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \frac{((1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha-1} c_i - (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha-1} c_{i-1})}{(1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha}}.
\end{aligned}$$

In such a case, it can be particularly useful to use an iterative numerical method to obtain the solutions of the above two equations simultaneously. We can obtain the maximum likelihood estimators $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ of the parameters α and β based on the above two equations, then the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_1(0; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta$ is $f_{G1}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) = \hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}$. The applications, included analysis of real data to investigate the proposed estimators that studied in this chapter will be given in Chapter 4.

CHAPTER THREE

WEIGHTED LOMAX MODELS FOR UNGROUPED AND GROUPED LINE TRANSECT DATA

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we introduce another new parametric models called the weighted Lomax models to estimate the parameter $f(0)$ and consequently to estimate D . Two new versions of the Lomax model are proposed. The moments and maximum likelihood estimators are derived. Two types of data; ungrouped and grouped are considered.

3.2 The Weighted Lomax Detection Function

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of n perpendicular distances follow the weighted Lomax detection function $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$, which is proposed to be,

$$g_2(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{2}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \right), x \geq 0, \alpha, \beta > 0$$

then $g_2(0; \alpha, \beta) = 1$ and $g_2'(0; \alpha, \beta) = 0$. The result $g_2'(0; \alpha, \beta) = 0$ indicates that $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ has a shoulder at the origin (i.e. at $x = 0$). The plots of $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ for some different values of α and β are depicted in Figure (3.1).

As another proposed detection function, we suggest and consider the following weighted Lomax detection function

$$g_3(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{4}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}\right)^2, \quad x \geq 0, \alpha, \beta > 0.$$

This detection function also satisfies the shoulder condition assumption ($g_3'(0; \alpha, \beta) = 0$) and also satisfies the property that the probability of detecting an object on the line itself is one (i.e. $g_3(0; \alpha, \beta) = 1$). Figure (3.2) displays the shapes of $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ for some values of α and β .

For fixed values of α and β , there is relationships between the three detection functions $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (classical Lomax detection function), $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$, which are given as follows

$$\begin{aligned} g_2(x; \alpha, \beta) &= 2g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)(1 - g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)/2) \\ &= g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)(2 - g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} g_3(x; \alpha, \beta) &= 4g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) \left(1 - \sqrt{g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}/2\right)^2 \\ &= g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) \left(2 - \sqrt{g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)}\right)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma (3.1): For fixed values of α and β

$$g_1(x; \alpha, \beta) \leq g_2(x; \alpha, \beta) \leq g_3(x; \alpha, \beta), \quad \forall x \geq 0$$

and the equality of three detection functions occurs at $x = 0$.

Proof: For simplicity, Let $g_1 = g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $g_2 = g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3 = g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ then

$g_2 \geq g_1$, if and only if, $g_1(2 - g_1) \geq g_1$, if and only if, $2 - g_1 \geq 1$, if and only if, $g_1 \leq 1$, if and only if, $(1 + \beta x)^{-\alpha-1} \leq 1$, if and only if, $1 + \beta x \geq 1$,

if and only if, $\beta x \geq 0$, which is true for all $\beta, x > 0$. Also, $g_2 = g_1$, if and only if, $\beta x = 0$ and since $\beta > 0$ then $g_2 = g_1$, if and only if, $x = 0$.

For the other part of the above lemma,

$g_3 \geq g_2$, if and only if, $g_1(2 - \sqrt{g_1})^2 \geq g_1(2 - g_1)$, if and only if, $(2 - \sqrt{g_1})^2 \geq 2 - g_1$, if and only if, $g_1 - 4\sqrt{g_1} + 4 \geq 2 - g_1$, if and only if, $2g_1 - 4\sqrt{g_1} \geq -2$, if and only if, $g_1 - 2\sqrt{g_1} + 1 \geq 0$, if and only if, $(1 - \sqrt{g_1})^2 \geq 0$, which is true for any value of g_1 . Also, $(1 - \sqrt{g_1})^2 = 0$, if and only if, $g_1 = 1$, if and only if, $(1 + \beta x)^{-\alpha-1} = 1$, if and only if, $x = 0$.

This completes the proof.

The above lemma indicates that for a specific object, given that its perpendicular distance is x , then the probability of detecting the object based on $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is greater than the probability of detecting it based on $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ or $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$. Also the probability of detecting based on $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is greater than that based on $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$. For $\alpha = 2$ and $\beta = 0.4$, Figure (3.3) demonstrates the plots of the three detection functions $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$.

3.3 The Weighted Lomax Probability Density Function

For purpose of estimation, we need to determine the *pdf* that corresponds $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and that corresponds $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$. If the detection function is $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ then

$$\int_0^{\infty} g_2(x; \alpha, \beta) dx = \frac{2 + 3\alpha}{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)}.$$

and if the detection function is $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ then

$$\int_0^{\infty} g_3(x; \alpha, \beta) dx = \frac{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4}{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)(1 + 3\alpha)}.$$

Since the probability density function corresponds $g_i(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is $f_i(x; \alpha, \beta) = k_i g_i(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $i = 2, 3$, where $k_i = 1/\int_0^{\infty} g_i(x; \alpha, \beta) dx$ then

$$f_2(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)}{2 + 3\alpha} \frac{2}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}}\right) \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$f_3(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)(1 + 3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \frac{4}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}\right)^2 \quad (3.2)$$

where $x \in [0, \infty)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in (0, \infty)$ for both probability density functions. We named the two functions $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ as weighted Lomax functions because each function consists of a number of classical Lomax distributions with some weights. To clarify that, we consider the following illustrations:

Remember that the classical Lomax distribution is denoted by $LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$. That is, if $X \sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$ then the *pdf* of X is $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, which is given by Formula (2.1). Now,

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(x; \alpha, \beta) &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)}{2 + 3\alpha} \frac{2}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}}\right) \\ &= \frac{2(1 + 2\alpha)}{2 + 3\alpha} \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} - \frac{\alpha}{2 + 3\alpha} \frac{\beta(1 + 2\alpha)}{(1 + \beta x)^{2\alpha+2}} \\ &= \frac{2(1 + 2\alpha)}{2 + 3\alpha} LD(\alpha + 1, \beta) - \frac{\alpha}{2 + 3\alpha} LD(2\alpha + 2, \beta). \end{aligned}$$

That is, $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ consists of two Lomax distributions with weights $\frac{2(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha}$ and $\frac{-\alpha}{2+3\alpha}$. The sum of the two weights is one. In the same way, we can illustrate that $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ can be expressed as a function of the classical Lomax distribution with specific weights.

Let $a_1 = \frac{4(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4}$, $a_2 = \frac{-8\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4}$ and $a_3 = \frac{\alpha(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4}$ then

$$\begin{aligned} f_3(x; \alpha, \beta) &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \frac{4}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}\right)^2 \\ &= \alpha\beta a_1 \frac{1}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} - \alpha\beta a_1 \frac{1}{(1+\beta x)^{(3\alpha+3)/2}} + \alpha\beta a_1 \frac{1}{4(1+\beta x)^{2\alpha+2}} \\ &= a_1 \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} + a_2 \frac{((3\alpha+1)/2)\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{(3\alpha+3)/2}} + a_3 \frac{(2\alpha+1)\beta}{4(1+\beta x)^{2\alpha+2}} \\ &= a_1 LD(\alpha+1, \beta) + a_2 LD((3\alpha+3)/2, \beta) + a_3 LD(2\alpha+2, \beta). \end{aligned}$$

(Note that: $a_1 = \frac{-(1+3\alpha)}{2\alpha} a_2 = \frac{4(1+2\alpha)}{\alpha} a_3$) Because $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ have a shoulder condition at the origin then $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ satisfied this property. That is, $f_2'(0; \alpha, \beta) = 0$ and $f_3'(0; \alpha, \beta) = 0$.

Figure (3.1). Some shapes of the weighted Lomax detection function, $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ for the values $\alpha = 0.5, 2, 5, 8$ and $\beta = 0.8$.

Figure (3.2). Some shapes of the weighted Lomax detection function, $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ for the values $\alpha = 0.5, 2, 5, 8$ and $\beta = 0.8$.

Figure (3.3). The shapes of $g_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 0.4$.

3.4 Moments Estimators under Ungrouped Data

The parameters $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ need to be estimated. The method of moments can be implemented to estimate the required parameters. To apply the moments method, we need to derive the first and second moments of $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$.

3.4.1 Moments Estimators of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$

In general, the k^{th} moment for $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (i.e. the weighted Lomax model given by Formula, 3.1) is,

$$\begin{aligned} EX^k &= \int_0^{\infty} x^k \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \frac{2}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}}\right) dx \\ &= \frac{2(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \int_0^{\infty} x^k \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} dx - \frac{\alpha}{2+3\alpha} \int_0^{\infty} x^k \frac{(1+2\alpha)\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{2\alpha+2}} dx \\ &= \frac{2(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} EY_1^k - \frac{\alpha}{2+3\alpha} EY_2^k. \end{aligned}$$

Where $Y_1 \sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$ and $Y_2 \sim LD(2\alpha + 2, \beta)$. By using Formula (2.2), we obtain,

$$EY_1^k = \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha - k)\Gamma(k + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}, \quad \alpha > k.$$

and

$$EY_2^k = \frac{2\alpha+1}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha-k+1)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+2)}, \quad 2\alpha + 1 > k \text{ or } \alpha > (k - 1)/2.$$

Because $k > (k - 1)/2$ and the two conditions $\alpha > k$ and $\alpha > (k - 1)/2$ then we conclude that $\alpha > k$. Therefore,

$$EX^k = \frac{\alpha(1 + 2\alpha)\Gamma(k + 1)}{\beta^k(2 + 3\alpha)} \left(\frac{2\Gamma(\alpha - k)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} - \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha - k + 1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 2)} \right), \quad \alpha > k.$$

By taking $k = 1$ and $k = 2$, yielding the first and second moments of the weighted Lomax distribution, $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$, respectively

$$\begin{aligned} EX &= \frac{7\alpha + 5}{2\beta(3\alpha^2 - \alpha - 2)} \\ &= \frac{7\alpha + 5}{\beta(\alpha - 1)(6\alpha + 4)}, \quad \alpha > 1, \beta > 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$EX^2 = \frac{3(5\alpha^2 + \alpha - 2)}{\beta^2(6\alpha^4 - 17\alpha^3 + 7\alpha^2 + 8\alpha - 4)}, \quad \alpha > 2, \beta > 0$$

The moments estimators of α and β do not exist in closed form. We can obtain them by solving the following two equations numerically with respect to α and β ,

$$\frac{7\alpha + 5}{\beta(\alpha - 1)(6\alpha + 4)} = \bar{X}$$

and

$$\frac{3(5\alpha^2 + \alpha - 2)}{\beta^2(6\alpha^4 - 17\alpha^3 + 7\alpha^2 + 8\alpha - 4)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n}.$$

If we fixed α as a known parameter then the moments estimator of β and consequently that of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$ are exists in closed form, which can be obtained by solving the equation

$$\frac{7\alpha + 5}{\beta(\alpha - 1)(6\alpha + 4)} = \bar{X},$$

which gives

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{7\alpha + 5}{(\alpha - 1)(6\alpha + 4)} \frac{1}{\bar{X}}, \quad \alpha > 1.$$

Table (3.1) gives some values of α and the corresponding moments estimators $\hat{\beta}$ and $\hat{f}_{M_2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ for $\alpha = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 10, 15, 30, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 10000$. Note that,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_{M_2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta}) &= \frac{\alpha \hat{\beta}(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \\ &= \frac{14\alpha^3 + 17\alpha^2 + 5\alpha}{18\alpha^3 + 6\alpha^2 - 16\alpha - 8} \frac{1}{\bar{X}}. \end{aligned}$$

As $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, $\hat{f}_{M_2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta}) \rightarrow \frac{7}{9\bar{X}}$. That is,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{14\alpha^3 + 17\alpha^2 + 5\alpha}{18\alpha^3 + 6\alpha^2 - 4\alpha - 8} \frac{1}{\bar{X}} \right) = \frac{7}{9\bar{X}}.$$

3.4.2 Moments Estimators of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$

The k^{th} moment for $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (the weighted Lomax model given by Formula, 3.2) is,

$$EX^k = \int_0^\infty x^k \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \frac{4}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}\right)^2 dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{4(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \int_0^\infty x^k \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{\alpha+1}} dx - \frac{8\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \int_0^\infty x^k \frac{(1+3\alpha)/2\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{(3\alpha+3)/2}} dx \\
&\quad + \frac{\alpha(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \int_0^\infty x^k \frac{(1+2\alpha)\beta}{(1+\beta x)^{2\alpha+2}} dx \\
&= \frac{4(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} EW_1^k - \frac{8\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} EW_2^k + \frac{\alpha(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} EW_3^k
\end{aligned}$$

where $W_1 \sim LD(\alpha + 1, \beta)$, $W_2 \sim LD((3\alpha + 3)/2, \beta)$ and $W_3 \sim LD(2\alpha + 2, \beta)$. By using Formula (2.2), we obtain,

$$EW_1^k = \frac{\alpha}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha - k)\Gamma(k + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}, \quad \alpha > k,$$

$$EW_2^k = \frac{2\alpha+1}{2\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(3\alpha/2-k+1/2)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma((3\alpha+3)/2)}, \quad (3\alpha + 1)/2 > k \text{ or } \alpha > (2k - 1)/2,$$

and

$$EW_3^k = \frac{2\alpha+1}{\beta^k} \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha-k+1)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+2)}, \quad 2\alpha + 1 > k \text{ or } \alpha > (k - 1)/2,$$

Because $k > k - \frac{1}{2} > (k - 1)/2$ then the constraints $\alpha > k$, $\alpha > (2k - 1)/2$ and $\alpha > (k - 1)/2$ occur together if $\alpha > k$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
EX^k &= \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)\Gamma(k+1)}{\beta^k(11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4)} * \\
&\quad \left(\frac{4\Gamma(\alpha-k)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} - \frac{4\Gamma(3\alpha/2-k+1/2)}{\Gamma((3\alpha+3)/2)} + \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha-k+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+2)} \right), \alpha > k.
\end{aligned}$$

If $k = 1$ then

$$EX = \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{\beta(11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4)} \left(\frac{4}{\alpha(\alpha-1)} - \frac{16}{(3\alpha+1)(3\alpha-1)} + \frac{1}{2\alpha(2\alpha+1)} \right), \alpha > 1,$$

and if $k = 2$ then

$$EX^2 = \frac{2\alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{\beta^2(11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4)} \left(\frac{4}{\alpha(\alpha-1)(\alpha-2)} - \frac{4\Gamma(3\alpha/2-3/2)}{\Gamma((3\alpha+3)/2)} + \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha-1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+2)} \right), \alpha > 2.$$

Again, the moments estimators of α and β do not exist in closed form, but they can be obtained by solving the two equations simultaneously,

$$EX = \bar{X} \text{ and } EX^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n},$$

with respect to α and β , where EX and EX^2 were given above. If we fixed α as a known parameter then the moments estimator of β and consequently that of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ are exists in closed form. In this case,

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{(11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4)} \left(\frac{4}{\alpha(\alpha-1)} - \frac{16}{(3\alpha+1)(3\alpha-1)} + \frac{1}{2\alpha(2\alpha+1)} \right) \frac{1}{\bar{X}},$$

and

$$f_{M3}(x; \alpha, \hat{\beta}) = \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2+13\alpha+4} \hat{\beta}.$$

Table (3.2) gives some values of α and the corresponding moments estimators $\hat{\beta}$ and $\hat{f}_{M3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ for $\alpha = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 10, 15, 30, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 10000$. Note that,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \infty} (f_{M3}(x; \alpha, \hat{\beta})) = \frac{89}{121\bar{X}}.$$

Table (3.1). The expected values of X , the moments estimator $\hat{f}_{M_2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$, where $\alpha = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 10, 15, 30, 50, 100, 500, 1000$ and 10000 .

α	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
EX	$\frac{1.1875}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.5909}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.3928}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.2941}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.2350}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1956}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1675}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1465}{\beta}$
$\hat{\beta}$	$\frac{1.1875}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.5909}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.3928}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.2941}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.2350}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.1956}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.1675}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.1465}{\bar{X}}$
$\hat{f}_2(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$	$\frac{1.4843}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{1.1280}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{1.0102}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.9515}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.9165}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8931}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8765}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8641}{\bar{X}}$

α	10	15	30	50	100	500	1000	10000
EX	$\frac{0.1302}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0836}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0403}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0238}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0118}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0023}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0012}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0001}{\beta}$
$\hat{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1302}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0836}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0403}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0238}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0118}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0023}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0012}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0001}{\bar{X}}$
$\hat{f}_2(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$	$\frac{0.8544}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8270}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8015}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7918}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7847}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7792}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7785}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7780}{\bar{X}}$

Table (3.2). The expected values of X , the moments estimator $\hat{f}_{M3}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$, where $\alpha = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 10, 15, 30, 50, 100, 500, 1000$ and 10000 .

α	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
EX	$\frac{1.5068}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.7253}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.4747}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.3522}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.2797}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.2319}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1980}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1727}{\beta}$
$\hat{\beta}$	$\frac{1.5068}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7253}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.4747}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.3522}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.2797}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.2319}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.1980}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.1727}{\bar{X}}$
$\hat{f}_3(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$	$\frac{1.4253}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{1.0727}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.9576}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.9009}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8671}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8448}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8289}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.8171}{\bar{X}}$

α	10	15	30	50	100	500	1000	10000
EX	$\frac{0.1531}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0836}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0468}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0276}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0118}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0027}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0014}{\beta}$	$\frac{0.0001}{\beta}$
$\hat{\beta}$	$\frac{0.1531}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0836}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0468}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0276}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0118}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0027}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0014}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.0001}{\bar{X}}$
$\hat{f}_3(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$	$\frac{0.8079}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7818}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7577}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7487}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7420}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7368}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7362}{\bar{X}}$	$\frac{0.7356}{\bar{X}}$

3.5 Maximum Likelihood Estimators under Ungrouped Data

For a purpose of finding the maximum likelihood estimators of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$, we need to find the maximum likelihood estimators for parameters α and β .

3.5.1 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$

The likelihood function $l_2(\alpha, \beta)$ based on $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (Model 3.1) is

$$\begin{aligned} l_2(\alpha, \beta) &= \prod_{i=1}^n f_2(x_i; \alpha, \beta) \\ &= \left(\frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{2}{(1+\beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The log likelihood function is

$$\begin{aligned} \log l_2(\alpha, \beta) &= n\{\log\alpha + \log\beta + \log(1+2\alpha) - \log(2+3\alpha)\} \\ &\quad -(\alpha+1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+\beta x_i) + \sum_{i=1}^n \log\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}(1+\beta x_i)^{-\alpha-1}\right) + \text{constant} \end{aligned}$$

The maximum likelihood estimators for α and β are obtained by solving the following two equations simultaneously,

$$\frac{\partial \log l_2(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \log l_2(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

where ,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \log l_2(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} &= \frac{6n\alpha^2 + 8n\alpha + 2n}{6\alpha^3 + 7\alpha^2 + 2\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+\beta x_i) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(1+\beta x_i)^{-\alpha-1} \log(1+\beta x_i)}{1 - \frac{1}{2}(1+\beta x_i)^{-\alpha-1}} \\ &= \frac{2n(63 + 4\alpha + 1)}{\alpha(1+2\alpha)(2+3\alpha)} + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+\beta x_i) \frac{1 - (1+\beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}}{2(1+\beta x_i)^{\alpha+1} - 1} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \log l_2(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} &= \frac{n}{\beta} - (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{1 + \beta x_i} + (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i(1 + \beta x_i)^{-\alpha-2}}{2 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{-\alpha-1}} \\ &= \frac{n}{\beta} + 2(\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{1 + \beta x_i} \frac{1 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}}{2(1 + \beta x_i)^{\alpha+1} - 1}\end{aligned}$$

The solution of the above two equations can be determined by using a suitable numerical methods such as the Newton-Raphson method. Let $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ be the maximum likelihood estimator for α and β respectively, then the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$ is $f_{ML2}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$.

As $n \rightarrow \infty$, $f_{ML2}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ is asymptotically $N(f_2(0; \alpha, \beta), \sigma_f^2)$, $\sigma_f^2 = \frac{1}{n} A' I^{-1}(\alpha, \beta) A$, where A' : The column vector. A is estimated by using $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ as an estimators for α and β respectively. Also the Fisher information matrix $I(\alpha, \beta)$ is estimated by using the empirical Hessian matrix $H(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ (Buckland *et al.*, 2001). The elements of A , $I(\alpha, \beta)$ and $H(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ were exhibited in Section (2.4).

3.5.2 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$

The likelihood function $l_3(\alpha, \beta)$ based on $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ (Model 3.2) is

$$\begin{aligned}l_3(\alpha, \beta) &= \prod_{i=1}^n f_3(x_i; \alpha, \beta) \\ &= \left(\frac{\alpha\beta(1 + 2\alpha)(1 + 3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{4}{(1 + \beta x_i)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x_i)^{(\alpha+1)/2}} \right)^2.\end{aligned}$$

The log likelihood function is

$$\log l_3(\alpha, \beta) = n\{\log\alpha + \log\beta + \log(1 + 2\alpha) + \log(1 + 3\alpha) - \log(11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4)\} \\ -(\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + \beta x_i) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}(1 + \beta x_i)^{-(\alpha+1)/2}\right) + \text{constant}$$

The maximum likelihood estimators for α and β are obtained by solving the following two equations simultaneously,

$$\frac{\partial \log l_3(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \log l_3(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

where ,

$$\frac{\partial \log l_3(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = n \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{2}{1 + 2\alpha} + \frac{3}{1 + 3\alpha} - \frac{22\alpha + 13}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \right\} \\ + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(-\log(1 + \beta x_i) + \frac{(1 + \beta x_i)^{-(\alpha+1)/2} \log(1 + \beta x_i)}{2 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{-(\alpha+1)/2}} \right) \\ = n \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{2}{1 + 2\alpha} + \frac{3}{1 + 3\alpha} - \frac{22\alpha + 13}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \right\} \\ + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\log(1 + \beta x_i) \frac{1 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}{2(1 + \beta x_i)^{(\alpha+1)/2} - 1} \right)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l_3(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = \frac{n}{\beta} - (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{1 + \beta x_i} + (\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i (1 + \beta x_i)^{-(\alpha+3)/2}}{2 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{-(\alpha+1)/2}} \\ = \frac{n}{\beta} + 2(\alpha + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{1 + \beta x_i} \frac{1 - (1 + \beta x_i)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}{2(1 + \beta x_i)^{(\alpha+1)/2} - 1}$$

A numerical method is needed to find the solution of the above two equations with respect to α and β . If $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ are the maximum likelihood estimator of α and β respectively, then the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ is $f_{ML3}(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$.

3.6 Maximum Likelihood Estimators under Grouped Data

By using the same notations of Subsection (1.3.2), each cell probability P_i has the following expression

$$P_i = \int_{c_{i-1}}^{c_i} f_j(x; \alpha, \beta) dx = F_j(c_i) - F_j(c_{i-1}), \quad \begin{matrix} i = 1, 2, \dots, k \\ j = 2, 3 \end{matrix},$$

where $F_j(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function corresponding the density function $f_j(x; \alpha, \beta)$, $j = 2, 3$ and P_i is a function of the parameters α and β .

3.6.1 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_2(\mathbf{0}; \alpha, \beta)$ (Grouped Data)

To find P_i , we need to find the cumulative distribution function corresponding the density function $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$, which can be found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_2(x) &= p(X \leq x) \\ &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \int_0^x \frac{2}{(1+\beta t)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta t)^{\alpha+1}}\right) dt \end{aligned}$$

By using the transformation $u = 1 + \beta t$, then $t = \frac{u-1}{\beta}$ and $dt = \frac{1}{\beta} du$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} F_2(x) &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \int_0^x 2u^{-\alpha-1} \left(1 - \frac{2u^{-2\alpha-2}}{2}\right) \frac{1}{\beta} du \\ &= \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \int_1^{1+\beta x} (2u^{-\alpha-1} - u^{-2\alpha-2}) du \\ &= \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha} (1 - (1+\beta x)^{-\alpha}) + \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} ((1+\beta x)^{-2\alpha-1} - 1) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$P_i = F_2(c_i) - F_2(c_{i-1}) \\ = \frac{\alpha(1+2\alpha)}{2+3\alpha} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha} \{ (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1+\beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \} + \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} \{ (1+\beta c_i)^{-2\alpha-1} - (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-2\alpha-1} \} \right).$$

For a given grouped data set, the log likelihood function is defined by (Burnham et al., 1980)

$$\log l_{G2}(\alpha, \beta) = \log \left(\frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! \dots n_k!} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \log P_i .$$

The maximum likelihood estimators of α and β are the solutions of the following two equations

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G2}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \log l_{G2}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0,$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G2}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \log P_i$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G2}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \log P_i$$

Let

$$U1 = (1+\beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \left\{ \frac{2}{\alpha} \left(\log(1+\beta c_i) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) - \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} (1+\beta c_i)^{-\alpha-1} \left(\log(1+\beta c_i) + \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} \right) \right\} \\ + (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} \left\{ \frac{2}{2\alpha+1} (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha-1} \left(\log(1+\beta c_{i-1}) + \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} \right) - \frac{2}{\alpha} \left(\log(1+\beta c_{i-1}) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) \right\},$$

$$U2 = \frac{2}{\alpha} \{ (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1+\beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \} + \frac{1}{2\alpha+1} \{ (1+\beta c_i)^{-2\alpha-1} - (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-2\alpha-1} \}$$

and

$$U3 = 2 \{ (1+\beta c_i)^{-\alpha-1} c_i - (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha-1} c_{i-1} \} + \{ (1+\beta c_{i-1})^{-2\alpha-2} c_{i-1} - (1+\beta c_i)^{-2\alpha-2} c_i \}$$

A simple but tedious steps lead to,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \log P_i = \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{2}{1+2\alpha} - \frac{3}{1+3\alpha} + \frac{U1}{U2}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \log P_i = \frac{U3}{U2}.$$

Solving the above equations can be accomplished by using an iterative numerical method such as the Newton-Raphson method, which give the maximum likelihood estimators of α and β (say $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$). Then the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_2(0; \alpha, \beta)$ by using the grouped data is

$$\hat{f}_{GML2}(0) = \frac{\hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}(1+2\hat{\alpha})}{2+3\hat{\alpha}}.$$

3.6.2 Maximum Likelihood Estimator of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ (Grouped Data)

The cumulative distribution function corresponding the probability density function $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} F_3(x) &= p(X \leq x) \\ &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)}{11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4} \int_0^x \frac{4}{(1+\beta t)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\beta t)^{(\alpha+1)/2}}\right)^2 dt. \end{aligned}$$

The transformation $u = 1 + \beta t$ gives $t = \frac{u-1}{\beta}$ and $dt = \frac{1}{\beta} du$. Let $C = \alpha(1+2\alpha)(1+3\alpha)/(11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4)$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} F_3(x) &= 4C \int_1^{1+\beta x} (u^{-\alpha-1} - u^{-(3\alpha+3)/2} + \frac{1}{4}u^{-2\alpha-2}) du \\ &= 4C \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha} (1 - (1+\beta x)^{-\alpha}) + \frac{2}{3\alpha+1} ((1+\beta x)^{-\frac{3\alpha+1}{2}} - 1) + \frac{1}{4(2\alpha+1)} (1 - (1+\beta x)^{-(2\alpha+1)}) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
P_i &= F_3(c_i) - F_3(c_{i-1}) \\
&= 4C \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \{ (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \} + \frac{2}{3\alpha + 1} \{ (1 + \beta c_i)^{-(3\alpha+1)/2} - (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-(3\alpha+1)/2} \} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{4(2\alpha + 1)} \{ (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-2\alpha-1} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-2\alpha-1} \} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\log P_i = \log 4 + \log C + \log V$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
V &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \{ (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-\alpha} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-\alpha} \} + \frac{2}{3\alpha + 1} \{ (1 + \beta c_i)^{-(3\alpha+1)/2} - (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-(3\alpha+1)/2} \} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{4(2\alpha + 1)} \{ (1 + \beta c_{i-1})^{-2\alpha-1} - (1 + \beta c_i)^{-2\alpha-1} \}
\end{aligned}$$

For a given grouped data set, the log likelihood function is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\log l_{G3}(\alpha, \beta) &= \log \left(\frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! \dots n_k!} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \log P_i \\
&= \log \left(\frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! \dots n_k!} \right) + n \{ \log \alpha + \log(2\alpha + 1) + \log(3\alpha + 1) - \log(11\alpha^2 + 13\alpha + 4) \} + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \log V
\end{aligned}$$

The maximum likelihood estimators of α and β are the solutions of the following two equations

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G3}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \log l_{G3}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = 0,$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G3}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} P_i$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \log l_{G3}(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{P_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} P_i .$$

The numerical solution of the above two equations with respect to α and β gives the maximum likelihood estimators $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ of α and β respectively. Therefore, the maximum likelihood estimator of $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ using the grouped data is

$$\hat{f}_{GML3}(0) = \frac{\hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}(1 + 2\hat{\alpha})(1 + 3\hat{\alpha})}{11\hat{\alpha}^2 + 13\hat{\alpha} + 4} .$$

CHAPTER FOUR

REAL DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

The implementation of the resultant estimators that developed in this thesis using a real data can give more space to understand, manipulate and develop these estimators and to be familiar with the places of implementation for these estimators.

4.2 Real Data Description

The laake stakes data set which is given in Burnham *et al.*, (1980) is reanalyzed here by applying the proposed estimators. The data were collected by using line transect technique to estimate the density of stakes. These data are perpendicular distances (in meters) of detected stakes from the transect line. In this experiment, the investigator was placed 150 stakes at random in an area of $L = 1000$ meters long. Out of 150 stakes, 68 stakes were detected and their perpendicular distances x_i are recorded.

The true *pdf* $f(x)$ for the perpendicular distances is unknown, but the true density of stakes is known and equals $D = 0.00375 \text{ stakes}/m^2$ or $D = 37.5 \text{ stakes}/\text{hectare}$ which gives the true value of $f(0)$ to be 0.110294. The last value of $f(0)$ can be obtained from the formula

$D = nf(0)/2L$. The perpendicular distances x_i for the 68 stakes are reproduced in Table (4.1).

4.3 Estimators and Results

All proposed estimators that derived in Chapters 2 and 3 were computed. The proposed estimators of Chapter 2 are $\hat{f}_{M1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{ML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, which are derived under the Lomax model for ungrouped and grouped data, where $\hat{f}_{M1}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ is the moments estimator, $\hat{f}_{ML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ is the ML estimator for ungrouped data and $\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ is the ML estimator of $f(0, \alpha, \beta)$ for grouped data.

The proposed estimators of Chapter (3) are the moments estimators $\hat{f}_{M2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{M3}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$, which are derived under the weighted Lomax models $f_2(x, \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x, \alpha, \beta)$ respectively. The two estimators are computed for $\alpha = 2, 3, 5, 6, 10, 100, 500, 1000$ as shown in Table (4.3). Moreover, the ML estimators $\hat{f}_{ML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{ML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ under the weighted Lomax models $f_2(x, \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_3(x, \alpha, \beta)$ are computed. Finally, the ML estimators $\hat{f}_{GML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{GML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ under the weighted Lomax models for grouped data are also computed. Note that the sample mean of the 68 perpendicular distances is 6.10824.

To compute the estimators $\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{GML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{GML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, the data were divided into six intervals with boundaries $C_0 = 0 = \min\{x_i\}$, $C_1 = 3.195$, $C_2 = 6.295$, $C_3 = 9.395$, $C_4 = 12.495$, $C_5 = 15.595$ and $C_6 = 31.31 = \max\{x_i\}$. These intervals and the corresponding frequencies are listed in Table (4.2). Remember that the exact value of D is 0.00375 stakes/ m^2 or $D = 37.5$ stakes/hectare. It is

worthwhile to mention here that the value of these estimators may be improved by increasing the number of intervals.

For comparison purposes, we evaluated the magnitudes of the estimators $f(0)$ under the negative exponential model and under the half-normal model. That is, we compute $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \beta)$, $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha)$. The estimators values are $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \beta) = 0.16371$ and $\hat{f}_{M1}(0; \alpha) = 0.09823$, which gives the estimators for D as 0.00557 and 0.00334 respectively. The values of the different proposed estimators of $f(0)$ and the corresponding estimators for D (multiplied by 10000) are listed in Table (4.3).

The study results show good statistical properties of the proposed estimators that derived under $\hat{f}_{GML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{M3}(0, 1000, \hat{\beta})$. They seem to be the most nearly closest to the true parameter $f(0)$ and then D . While $\hat{f}_{M1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{ML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{ML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{ML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, $\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and lastly $\hat{f}_{GML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ are considered to be as an overestimate parameters comparing with the true parameter.

The values of $\hat{f}_{M2}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ for $\alpha = 2, 3, 5, 6, 10, 100, 500, 1000$ are always better than the corresponding values of $\hat{f}_{M3}(0, \alpha, \hat{\beta})$ for the same values of α . For grouped data, the ML estimator $\hat{f}_{GML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ is better than the ML estimators $\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{f}_{GML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ on the basis of their closest to the true value of $f(0)$ and D .

TABLE (4.1). Laake Stakes Data.

The data displayed below are perpendicular distances in meters and appear on page 62 of Burnham *et al.* (1980). The true number of objects (stakes) is known and hence the true density is also known. It was found that $n = 68$, $L = 1000$ and $D = 0.00375$ stakes per square meter and the true density $f(x)$ is unknown.

Number	Perpendicular Distance(x)						
1	02.02	18	01.61	35	03.79	52	08.49
2	00.45	19	31.31	36	15.24	53	06.08
3	10.40	20	06.50	37	03.47	54	00.40
4	03.61	21	08.27	38	03.05	55	09.33
5	00.92	22	04.85	39	07.93	56	00.53
6	01.00	23	01.47	40	18.15	57	01.23
7	03.40	24	18.60	41	10.05	58	01.67
8	02.90	25	00.41	42	04.41	59	04.53
9	08.16	26	00.40	43	01.27	60	03.12
10	06.47	27	00.20	44	13.72	61	03.05
11	05.66	28	11.59	45	06.25	62	06.60
12	02.95	29	03.17	46	03.59	63	04.40
13	03.96	30	07.10	47	09.04	64	04.97
14	00.09	31	10.71	48	07.68	65	03.17
15	11.82	32	03.86	49	04.89	66	07.67
16	14.23	33	06.05	50	09.10	67	18.16
17	02.44	34	06.24	51	03.25	68	04.08

TABLE (4.2). The interval boundaries of six intervals for perpendicular distances of stake data and the corresponding number of observations.

Number of intervals	Boundaries of intervals	Number of observations
1	0.000-3.195	23
2	3.195-6.295	19
3	6.295-9.395	14
4	9.395-12.495	5
5	12.495-15.595	3
6	15.595-31.31	4

TABLE (4.3). Point estimates of $f(0)$ and D using the different proposed estimators. The exact value of D is 37.5 stakes per square hectare.

Estimator	$\hat{f}_{M1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{ML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{GML1}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{ML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{GML2}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{ML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{GML3}(0, \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$
$f(0)$	0.144929	0.187775	0.191405	0.146200	0.129649	0.144157	0.118897
D	49.2758	63.8435	65.0778	49.6900	44.0806	49.0100	40.4249

Estimator	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,2, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,3, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,5, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,6, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,10, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,100, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,500, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M2}(0,1000, \hat{\beta})$
$f(0)$	0.243000	0.184669	0.155773	0.150043	0.139877	0.128466	0.127565	0.127451
D	82.6199	62.7874	52.9629	51.0147	47.5581	43.6784	43.3723	43.3333

Estimator	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,2, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,3, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,5, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,6, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,10, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,100, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,500, \hat{\beta})$	$\hat{f}_{M3}(0,1000, \hat{\beta})$
$f(0)$	0.233341	0.175615	0.147489	0.141956	0.132264	0.121475	0.120624	0.120526
D	79.3358	59.7092	50.1464	48.2650	44.9698	41.3016	41.0122	40.9788

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORKS

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter we exhibit some important future works with some general conclusions corresponding the main findings of this thesis.

5.2 Conclusions

The main results of this thesis can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The classical Lomax model $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ isn't very dealing for line transect data. It doesn't satisfy the shoulder condition. However, it achieves the monotonically decreasing property. This model produces an estimator for $f(0)$, which is overestimating the corresponding estimator that derived under the negative exponential model.
- 2) The weighted Lomax model $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ satisfies the shoulder condition assumption and the monotonically decreasing property. Based on the real data this model seems to be better than the classical Lomax model.

- 3) The weighted Lomax model $f_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is very promising and very dealing to estimate the population abundance using line transects data. It satisfies the shoulder condition assumption and the monotonically decreasing property. The model seems to be better than $f_1(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $f_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ based on the real data set.
- 4) Since the Lomax and the weighted Lomax models depend on two parameters, they are flexible to fit a lot of line transect data sets.
- 5) The proposed parametric model $f_3(0; \alpha, \beta)$ can also be used for another purpose. It can be used to construct the nonparametric kernel estimator. More specifically, it can be used to compute the smoothing parameter of the kernel estimator, which plays a very vital role in the performance of the kernel estimator (see also ,Eidous and Alsalman,2013).

5.3 Suggestions for Future Works

There is an intensive space for future works; we indicate some of them below

- ❖ The Lomax and the weighted Lomax models are studied for un-truncated data. On the other hand, the perpendicular distances are sometimes be truncated at some distance. The Lomax and the weighted Lomax models might be studied for such of these data. That is, it is possible to develop these models when the range of x is $(0, w)$ not $(0, \infty)$.

- ❖ It is possible to construct confidence intervals for the parameter $f(0)$ based on the Lomax and the weighted Lomax models. Due to the approximate normality of $f(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$, then Large-sample $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ confidence interval (C.I.) for $f(0; \alpha, \beta)$ is given by

$$f(0; \hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) \pm Z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sqrt{\hat{\sigma}_f^2}, \text{ where } Z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \text{ is a value on the horizontal axis at which area to right is } \frac{\alpha}{2} \text{ under the standard normal curve.}$$

- ❖ We may study our models when $g(0) < 1$. This could happen when some objects are underground or under water or simply hidden by vegetations or anything according to area nature when the observer passes. To solve this problem we may combine capture-recapture methods with distance sampling method.
- ❖ We may insert the order statistics or the ranked set sampling when collecting line transect data under these models.
- ❖ We may use the Horvitz-Thompson method to estimate the density of the objects based on these models.
- ❖ A general weighted Lomax detection function with three parameters is taken the form ,

$$g_4(x; \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \frac{2^\gamma}{(1 + \beta x)^{\alpha+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1 + \beta x)^{\frac{\alpha+1}{\gamma}}} \right)^\gamma, \quad x \geq 0, \alpha, \gamma, \beta > 0$$

Can be considered and studied. In this case, the two weighted Lomax models $g_2(x; \alpha, \beta)$ and $g_3(x; \alpha, \beta)$ are special cases of $g_4(x; \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ when $\gamma = 1$ and $\gamma = 2$ respectively.

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